

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

**BUILDING A STRONGER COMMUNITY IN STI STUDIES
FOR EFFECTIVE IMPACT: THE EXPERIENCE OF RISIS**

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Research Infrastructures (RIs) must demonstrate transparency, openness, and a commitment to addressing users' needs, thereby building lasting and productive relationships between scholars and stakeholders.

To ensure that research findings and resources provided have an impact on the scholar community and policy processes, researchers and stakeholders must work collaboratively. This involves active engagement with policymakers and the timely communication of research results in a format accessible to decision-makers.

The policy brief highlights the importance of community-driven actions to foster continuous growth and improvement, paving the way for a more inclusive, relevant, and impactful future for RISIS and its stakeholders.

RISIS enhanced the visibility of its resources through coordinated activities. Despite the increased visibility, the wider community has still shown superficial knowledge of the potential uses of RISIS datasets and services. The open challenge mainly rests on identifying ways to improve awareness and promote a broader understanding of RISIS offerings.

1. INTRODUCTION

As the RISIS Horizon 2020 project approaches at an end, it stands at a pivotal turning point toward the establishment of an AISBL, which calls for a thorough reflection on the challenges and achievements faced during the development of the research infrastructure.

This policy brief endeavours to delve into the lessons learned on ways to enhance community interactions, communication, dissemination, and training strategies within RISIS. By learning from these lessons, RISIS can maximize its impact, relevance, and sustainability, contributing meaningfully to societal advancement and policy development.

2. RISIS POSITIONING IN THE STI COMMUNITY

RISIS Community map

The RISIS Community, with over **2,000 participants**, has been consolidated and continues to expand thanks to **strategic activities** organized to engage a broader audience over time.

Furthermore, RISIS **actively encourages** a continuous feedback loop with stakeholders, enabling the adaptation of research priorities and communication strategies to meet evolving needs. By leveraging **effective communication channels** and engagement tools, RISIS aims to **enhance its impact**, strengthen collaboration with policymakers and European partners, and foster a **culture of Open Science** and data-driven decision-making in Science and Innovation studies.

The community map consists of four macro-area groups:

RISIS Partners. The consortium consists of **18 partners** from international universities and research organizations with **interdisciplinary research focuses**. Each partner is responsible for specific dataset families and plays a critical role in external communication and dissemination activities, including producing press releases, organizing local meetings, presenting RISIS at scientific conferences and events, and contributing to RISIS Newsletter circulation.

Scholars in STI and Neighboring R&D Fields. The core end-users of RISIS are scholars from the Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) field and other neighbouring research domains. RISIS actively engages with scholars through open training activities, programming events, and participative events tailored to different user groups.

Core Stakeholders and Policymakers. RISIS identifies and engages with key stakeholders and organizations, including relevant institutions, statistical offices, other projects, and initiatives. Policymakers at various levels are engaged through workshops, working sessions, and policy maker sessions, where research results and policy implications are presented and discussed.

Press and Media for General Public Engagement. RISIS recognizes the importance of engaging the public, and the press and media play a crucial role in disseminating research findings and raising awareness.

Figure 1. RISIS Community map

Key figures 2019/2023

The figures on dissemination and communication achieved during the RISIS project are quite impressive and have been extensively illustrated in Deliverables 2.3 and 2.6. We used a **combined strategy to engage** with end users, stakeholders, and policymakers, to share RISIS viewpoints and to gather internal/external insights, and adapting our approach based on research objectives, engagement scope, and stakeholder dynamics.

The **engagement strategy** consisted of five set of activities (see Figure 2).

The first set, aimed at **informing** the whole RISIS Community, considering all the users - potential and actual - registered in RISIS mailing lists and following RISIS social channels.

The second and the third set of activities aimed at **consulting** and **involving** RISIS community, mainly through awareness events (e.g., Research Seminars and Policymaker sessions).

The most relevant and critical levels of engagement to be achieved (to **collaborate** and to **empower**) are related to RISIS training activities and access to datasets, which required a user selection process and a specific programme and Code of Conduct to be respected (See Deliverables 2.2 and 2.3 for details and website).

Figure 2. RISIS Engagement chart

We recall here some data that can summarize the capability developed by RISIS to **penetrate the existing community of scholars and stakeholders** dealing with science and technology policy issues, thanks to the variety of the resources provided and the different channels used for their dissemination and engagement.

Currently, RISIS Users (Research Seminars, Policymakers sessions, and training registered participants) are **over 2,000** (last data on Deliverable 2.6).

On the training side, 16 courses were organized, with **600 participants** involved and 3,856 downloads of training materials from Zenodo.

On the scholars' engagement side, 31 research seminars were organized with **1,217 registered participants** involved and over 1,000 downloads of materials from Zenodo.

On the stakeholders' side, 14 policymaker sessions were organized with **842 registered participants**, and 15 Policy Briefs were produced, which received 2,036 downloads.

On the communication side, **website visits** were **20% higher in 2021** compared to the first six months of the communication activities; the **Twitter 'likes'** were **three times higher** from the first year (2019) to the end of the project (2023); from **689 visualizations of YouTube** videos in 2020 to about **33,000 visualizations in 2023**.

The figures clearly demonstrate the relevance of what RISIS produces which goes beyond the official contacts of the mailing list, highlighting the capability of the RIs to penetrate the field with an **effective engagement strategy**.

What users want

The mid-term **survey on users' needs** provided some insights into what the community wants to find in RISIS (see Deliverable 2.5). The survey was administered through an online questionnaire (Evans and Mathur, 2018) dealing with a set of activities developed (training, access to datasets, workshops, special sessions, communication). It was targeted to all people (internal to the RISIS project and external scholars and stakeholders) who had registered for RISIS activities and services. The dimensions analysed were:

- **Participation in RISIS activities:** information channels, intensity of participation in activities and access to services, perceived advantage of participation, motivation of non-participating to some activities, research outputs derived by participation.
- **Attractiveness of RISIS:** impact on research interests, satisfaction with activities and services, suggestions for improvements.
- **RISIS support:** assessment of the support provided concerning services and activities, evaluation of the quality of information received, rating of the support by teams, suggestions for improvement.
- **RISIS value:** main contribution to the STI research community, added value of RISIS activities and services, most valuable features and weaknesses in the RISIS infrastructure services, overall satisfaction.

Respondents indicated that the **most valuable benefits** derived from the RI were "Knowledge about **new methods and approaches**", "Improving the **quality of research outputs**", "**No costs** for using RISIS tools and services", and "**Enlarging my research network**". The **main perceived contribution** of RISIS to the STI research community, as reported by the users, is the **development of core datasets** for STI research and the development of **services** that enable

researchers to **enrich, integrate and treat data**. Thus, the relevance is particularly high in terms of research capabilities and quality, but also in terms of the networking facilitated by the RI.

3. SCHOLARS AND STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT FOR STRENGTHENING RIs

To enhance the **societal impact** of research and foster effective scholars and stakeholder engagement with research infrastructures, RISIS implemented a series of **interconnected policy implications** for the future.

Firstly, it strived to establish **national and international standards** that promote engagement. These standards encompass best practices, reporting requirements, and assessment criteria, ensuring a consistent and effective approach across various projects.

Promoting **open access to research outcomes**, such as data, publications, and reports, is vital for transparency and accountability. RISIS advocated for open access, ensuring that stakeholders, policymakers, and the general public can access and use research findings for **informed decision-making**.

Facilitating the **integration of research findings** into policy formulation processes is another critical step. RISIS established **direct communication channels between research infrastructures and relevant policymakers**, supporting the development of policy briefs and actionable recommendations.

Public engagement is essential to involve the broader community in research initiatives. RISIS in the future shall promote public forums, citizen science projects, and educational campaigns to raise awareness of the importance of research and its societal impact.

Finally, supporting **collaborative platforms** that facilitate interactions between research infrastructures, stakeholders, and policymakers can enhance engagement efforts, as **hubs for knowledge exchange**, collaboration, and joint problem-solving.

to lead to **more relevant, inclusive, and impactful research outcomes** that contribute to the improvement of society.

4. LESSON LEARNED AND FUTURE CHALLENGES

Actively engaging with both the scholar community and the stakeholders is strategic to **propel RISIS toward long-term success**, while fostering valuable collaborations with policymakers and other European research infrastructures.

Drawing on the insights from scholars and stakeholders, RISIS seeks to enhance its contributions to the empirical social sciences. By leveraging **participatory engagement**, the project endeavours to create a **sense of ownership and shared vision** within the RI's user community, ensuring that the infrastructure remains responsive to their needs and expectations.

One of the **critical aspects** of this participatory endeavour is to tailor communication and dissemination strategies that recognize the **diverse backgrounds and interests of the users**. By effectively communicating the value and relevance of the outputs, RISIS fostered a deeper understanding and appreciation across the whole community, solidifying commitment and active involvement.

For example, the production of a series of policy briefs was specifically aimed at empowering stakeholders to engage with and **effectively use the resources offered by RISIS**. At the same time, Research Seminars were mainly focused on presenting how to answer **new research questions by using RIs' resources** (data, methods, and tools). On the other hand, **innovative models of training** were mainly directed toward empowering scholars (first and foremost early career researchers) through **capacity-building opportunities**, equipping them with the skills and knowledge to effectively engage with research methods.

Therefore, to adapt to evolving needs, research infrastructures should establish a **continuous feedback loop between scholars and stakeholders** which allows for adjustments in research priorities and communication strategies, ensuring continued relevance and effectiveness.

In this respect, RIs in social science research can be useful **arenas for productive continuous interactions** between different actors (Molas Gallart and Tang, 2011; Benneworth et al., 2022).

The RISIS experience also demonstrates that research infrastructures should strive a **balance between academic rigour and practical relevance**. While maintaining scientific excellence, the research should address **real-world challenges** and produce actionable insights that can be implemented. Acknowledging the valuable input provided by stakeholders and demonstrating how it has influenced the project's outcomes reinforces their role and commitment.

However, **effective stakeholders' engagement** is a long-term commitment that requires **dedicated resources and strategies**. Research infrastructures should allocate resources to sustain engagement throughout their lifecycle and beyond, **ensuring continuous collaboration and impact**. By incorporating these principles into their approach to scholars' and stakeholders' engagement, research infrastructures can enhance their effectiveness and impact, and foster a collaborative environment that produces insights and solutions for society.

In conclusion, **successful users' engagement** with research infrastructures is **based on open communication**, collaboration, networking and a **continuous monitoring** to understand diverse users' needs.

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RISIS2 - European Research Infrastructure for Science, technology and Innovation policy Studies aims at building a data and services infrastructure supporting the development of a new generation of analyses and indicators on STI fields.

To develop a deeper understanding of knowledge dynamics and policy relevant evidence, RISIS goes beyond established quantitative indicators, developing positioning indicators, in order to reduce asymmetries in actors producing new knowledge, in places where knowledge is generated, and in themes addressed.

RISIS community is dealing with sensitive issues as social innovation, non-technological innovation, the role of PhDs in society, and portfolios of public funding instruments, studying both universities and firms.

RISIS Policy Brief Series aim at disseminating key results coming from RISIS2 to improve the use of data for evidence-based policy making. The outcomes are presented through short documents pointing out the main policy issues at stake, demonstrating the contribution provided by RISIS, and what new avenues for research are now open.

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